

Side Products in the Preparation of Ethyl 7-Chloro-4-Hydroxyquinoline-3-Carboxylate from Diethyl Ethoxymethylenemalonate and *m*-Chloroaniline¹

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Three side products (i) 7-chloro-1-ethyl-1 : 4 dihydro-4-oxoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IV), (ii) 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII), and (iii) 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4 (1H)-quinolone (VI) have been isolated during preparation of 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (I) from diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate (EMME) and *m*-chloroaniline. The pyrolytic behaviour of the ester ethyl 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylate (II) and possibly the purity of EMME play an important role in their formation.

Pyrolysis of the ester (II) in boiling diphenyl ether results in the formation of (a) ethyl 7-chloro-1-ethyl-1 : 4-dihydro-4-oxoquinoline-3-carboxylate (V), (b) 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline (III), (c) (VI) and (d) (VIII) with evolution of carbon dioxide. A reaction mechanism consistent with the experimental data has been suggested.

Ethyl 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylate (II), an intermediate for chloroquine and amodiaquine, may be prepared from *m*-chloroaniline and diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate (EMME)^{2,3}. During large scale preparation of the corresponding acid (I) by the above process three side products, namely, (i) 7-chloro-1-ethyl-1 : 4-dihydro-4-oxoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IV), (ii) 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII), and (iii) 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4(1H)-quinolone (VI), have been isolated. The present paper deals with their isolation, identification and the possible mode of their formation.

The UV spectra of (VI) in ethanol showed typical bifurcation of the two peaks at 248–255 $m\mu$ and at 326–339 $m\mu$ regions as found in 7-chloro-4-quinolones^{4,5}. Its IR spectra in Nujol showed no absorption band for -NH- group and revealed the presence of carbonyl group by peaks at 1634 cm^{-1} and 1629 cm^{-1} . It has been reported that the characteristic frequency for the carbonyl vibration in 4-quinolones ranges from 1618 and 1647 cm^{-1} and appears mostly around 1620 and 1630 cm^{-1} .^{6–10} From the spectral evidences it could be concluded that (VI) is a 7-chloro-4-quinolone with a substitution at 1-position which was confirmed by its synthesis from 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline (III).

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Ethylation of (III) with ethyl iodide in presence of sodium hydroxide has afforded 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4 (1H)-quinolone (VI), m.p. 187°, together with some 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII). Reaction of (VI) with bromine in acetic acid afforded 7-chloro-3-bromo-1-ethyl-4 (1H)-quinolone.

I, R = -COOH	IV, R = -COOH	VIII, R = H
II, R = -COOC ₂ H ₅	V, R = -COOC ₂ H ₅	IX, R = COOH
III, R = H	VI, R = -H	
	VII, R = -Br	

On oxidation with alkaline permanganate (IV) has afforded 4-chloro-N-acetylanthranilic acid and 4-chloro-N-ethylanthranilic acid. Decarboxylation of (IV) yielded (VI). Final confirmation of the structure of (IV) was obtained by comparison with an authentic sample¹¹.

The yield of the side products has been found to be dependent on the temperature during cyclisation and duration of heating. Interestingly, different batches of EMME used in the cyclisation under standardized conditions often led to the formation of the side products in significantly varied quantities. All these batches of EMME, however, conformed to the generally accepted specification *e.g.*, refractive index (D line) at 20° not less than 1.4600².

Cyclisation of purified samples of diethyl *m*-chloroanilinomethylenemalonate gave consistent good yields of the ester (II) but all the side products were also formed although in a relatively smaller quantity.

From this observation it appeared that the ester (II) itself was also involved in the formation of the side products under the conditions of the reaction. It has now been demonstrated that by heating the pure ester (II) in boiling diphenyl ether carbon dioxide evolved and the following products were formed: (i) ethyl 7-chloro-1-ethyl-1 : 4-dihydro-4-oxoquinoline-3-carboxylate (V), (ii) 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII), (iii) 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4-(1H)-quinolone (VI) and (iv) 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline (III).

The isolation of the compounds (V), (VI), and (VIII) indicated that the ethyl group in the ester (II) was involved in their formation. In explaining the formation of all the

11. N. Barton, A. F. Crowther, W. Hepworth, D. N. Richardson and G. W. Driver, British Patent, 830, 832 (1960); *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, 55, 7442.

products the following mechanism may be suggested :

The initial step in the reaction may be visualised as the formation of ethyl carbonium ion and the anion (A_1) \rightleftharpoons (A_2) (or their hydrogen bonded forms). The ethyl carbonium ion can react in two different ways:—

(a) $C_2H_5^+$ may attack the N atom in (II) with the formation of the intermediate cation (C_1) or its tautomer (C_2). From the cation the proton may be picked up by the anion (A_1) or (A_2) leading to the formation of (V) and (I). At the prevailing temperature (I) would decompose into (III) and carbon dioxide.

(b) $C_2H_5^+$ may also attack the oxygen atom in the anion (A_2) leading to the formation of 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX) which would decarboxylate at the high temperature to (VIII).

The compound (VI) was presumably formed by thermal rearrangement of (VIII). Such thermal rearrangements of 4-alkoxy-quinolines to 1-alkyl-4(1H)-quinolones have been reported¹²⁻¹⁴. It has now been demonstrated that when (VIII) was heated for 1 hr. at 250° partial conversion to (VI) occurred.

Pyrolysis of the ester (II) in presence of benzoic acid led to the formation of 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline (III), carbon dioxide and ethyl benzoate. This observation points out to the intermolecular nature of the reaction.

Examples of alkylation of tertiary amines, hydroxy or oxo, or thiol derivative of heterocyclic compounds by carbalkoxy group have been reported¹⁵⁻²². Jones observed that thermal decomposition of alkyl 2-thioimidazole-4-carboxylates yielded 2-alkylthioimidazoles and carbon dioxide, and 2-ethylthioimidazole could be obtained by heating 2-thioimidazole with ethyl benzoate¹⁹. Kametani *et al.* have obtained quaternary salts by a novel methylation of tertiary amines with methyl salicylate²¹. A mechanism involving the formation of methyl carbonium cation from the ester has been suggested. Markees has observed that thermal decomposition of dialkyl chelidamates and related esters led to the formation of 4-alkoxy and 1-alkyl-4-oxo derivatives of pyridine with evolution of carbon dioxide²².

All the above observations tend to substantiate the mechanism suggested for the formation of the products obtained by pyrolysis of the ester (II).

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22. D. G. Markees, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 3120.

After completion of our present work, we came across a recent publication by Markees on the thermal decomposition of ethyl 4-quinolonecarboxylates and related compounds²³. He has observed that pyrolysis of ethyl 4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylate led to the

formation of 4-ethoxyquinoline, 1-ethyl-4-(1H)-quinolone and carbon dioxide. No mechanism for the reaction has been suggested.

Although the pyrolytic behaviour of the ester (II) partially explained the appearance of side products in the preparation of (I), the wide variation in their quantity in cyclisation of unpurified diethyl *m*-chloroanilinemethylenemalonate remains yet to be explained. It appears that this is due to the presence of hitherto unidentified impurity in diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate. Further work on this aspect is in progress.

Another interesting observation was made during our studies on thermal rearrangement of 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline. It was noticed that if the compound was heated at 250° with benzoic acid, 7-chloro-4-hydroxy-quinoline (III) and ethyl benzoate were formed together with some amount of 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4(1H)-quinolone (VI). Cleavage of alkyl heterocyclic ethers like 2-ethoxybenzothiazole or 2-benzyloxybenzothiazole with acetic or benzoic acid to yield the corresponding hydroxy compound and carboxylic esters has been reported²⁴.

EXPERIMENTAL

B.ps. and m.ps. are uncorrected. Petrol ether refers to the fraction b.p. 69–80°. U.V. spectra were determined in ethanol. IR spectra²⁵ were determined in Nujol.

Isolation of 7-chloro-1-ethyl-1 : 4-dihydro-4-oxoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IV), 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4(1H)-quinolone (VI), and 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII). Crude molten *m*-chloroanilinemethylenemalonate, prepared from EMME (13.5 kg.) and *m*-chloroaniline (7.7 kg.), was added under stirring to boiling diphenyl ether (70 L.) during 15 min. and heating continued at 250° for 50 min., allowing the EtOH formed to escape²⁶. Hydrolysis with NaOH solution and subsequent acidification of the aqueous layer afforded crude 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (I) (10.2 to 12.6 kg., 75.56 to 93.35% yield), melting range 245°–266° (decomp) (lit.². 273–274°).

Fractional crystallisation of the above crude acid from AcOH afforded 7-chloro-1-ethyl-1 : 4-dihydro-4-oxoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid in fine white needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 279° (lit.¹¹ —274°). (Found : C, 57.65; H, 4.05; N, 5.55. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₀ClNO₃ : C, 57.25; H, 4.01; N, 5.57%). λ_{max} 254, 262, 319, 330 m μ (log ϵ 4.40, 4.42, 4.03, 4.01). ν_{max} 1708, 1689, 1608, 1553, 1546, 1502 cm⁻¹.

A simpler method of isolation of (IV), however, was to heat the crude acid (I) in refluxing Ph₂O for 1 hr., and extraction of the reaction mixture with Na₂CO₃ solution. Acidification of the extract afforded (IV); m.p. 279° (AcOH) (0.23–0.95 kg. per charge).

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25. By the courtesy of Dr. A. K. Sen, Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India.

26. Diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate (EMME) used in the preparations was from Kay-Fries Chemicals, Inc., 360, Lexington Avenue, New York 17, N.Y., U.S.A. All the batches conformed to the following specifications—Assay—98% min., Refractive Index @20%D—1.4600 min. Acidity (max.)—0.2% (as acetic acid).

The Ph_2O layer in the preparation of (I) was extracted with dil. HCl. On basification a brownish solid was obtained which was extracted with hot petrol ether. The residue was crystallised from water (charcoal) to give 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4(1H)-quinolone (VI) in fine white needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 187° . (Found : C, 63.94; H, 5.08; N, 6.52. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{ClNO}$ requires : C, 63.59; H, 4.85; N, 6.75%). λ_{max} 217, 248, 255, 326, 339 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.46, 4.39, 4.42, 4.11, 4.16). ν_{max} 1634, 1629, 1592, 1582, 1543, 1497 cm^{-1} .

The hydrochloride (EtOH) melts at 203° (Found : N, 5.29. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{ClNO}$. HCl requires : N, 5.74%) and the picrate (EtOH) at 208° (Found : N, 12.68. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{ClNO}$. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_7$ requires : N, 12.82%).

The petrol ether extract on working up afforded 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII), m.p. and mixed m.p. 105° (lit.²⁷ -103°). λ_{max} 227, 280, 288 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.71, 3.82, 3.83).

The amount of the side products obtainable from one charge was in the range 240–600 g. of (VIII) and 25–46 g. of (VI).

Preparation of 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4(1H)-quinolone (VI) : 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline (III) (10 g.) and NaOH (2.3 g.) were dissolved in EtOH (100 ml.) by refluxing. Et I (5 ml.) was added and refluxing continued for 4 hr. After distilling EtOH and Et I the residue was treated with water, filtered and air-dried. The material was then extracted with petrol ether. The residue was crystallised from water to afford (VI) as white needles (3.9 g.), m.p. 187° (Found : C, 63.82; H, 4.98; N, 6.63. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{ClNO}$ requires : C, 63.59; H, 4.85; N, 6.75%).

A sample of (VI), thus prepared, showed no depression of m.p. on admixture with sample of (VI) obtained as side product in preparation of (I) or that by decarboxylation of (IV).

Working up of the above petrol ether extract yielded 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII) (2.8 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 105° (lit.²⁷ -103°).

Bromination of (VI) : 7-chloro-1-ethyl-3-bromo-4(1H)-quinolone (VII) : Bromine in AcOH (30% w/v; 53 ml.) was added dropwise to a well-stirred solution of (VI) (20 g.) in AcOH (200 ml.) at $30-35^\circ$. The yellowish precipitate was collected, washed with NaOH solution (10%) and water, and crystallised from methanol to afford (VII) as fine needles (12.6 g.), m.p. 196° (Found : C, 46.53; H, 3.02; N, 5.04; $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ClBrNO}$ requires : C, 46.09; H, 3.17; N, 4.89%).

In the above experiment addition of bromine in excess led to the formation of a reddish-brown perbromide of indefinite m.p. which decomposed during crystallisation. Addition of acetone to the prebromide afforded 7-chloro-1-ethyl-3-bromo-4(1H)-quinolone (VII). m.p. 196° and bromoacetone, b.p. $64-65^\circ/50$ mm.

Oxidation of (IV) : Isolation of 4-chloro-N-acetylanthranilic acid and 4-chloro-N-ethylanthranilic acid : A solution of (IV) (75 g.) in NaOH (22 g.) and water (2250 ml.) was treated portionwise with KMnO_4 (10×30 g.) under stirring at $30-35^\circ$ during 32 hr. The charge was

decolourised by addition of EtOH and filtered. MnO_2 sludge was washed with water (3×800 ml.). The combined filtrate and washings were acidified with HCl (congo red) to give 4-chloro-N-acetylanthranilic acid (5.5 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 213–214° (lit²⁸ —214°).

The acidic filtrate, after removal of 4-chloro-N-acetylanthranilic acid, was neutralised with NaHCO_3 and concentrated (to 300 ml.). On acidification, under cooling (10°), a solid [m.p. 128–135° (decomp)] was obtained. The above solid was dissolved in water (500 ml.) and refluxed for 2 hr. during which CO_2 evolved and a precipitate was formed. The precipitate (20 g.) was collected and crystallised from ethanol to give 4-chloro-N-ethylanthranilic acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 214° (Found : C, 54.48; H, 5.19; N, 7.12. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{ClNO}_2$ requires C, 54.16; H, 5.05; N, 7.02%).

Preparation of 4-chloro-N-ethylanthranilic acid : To a solution of 4-chloroanthranilic acid (5 g.) and K_2CO_3 (2.5 g.) in water (15 ml.), EtI (3 ml.) was added and refluxed for 4 hr. The precipitate was collected, and crystallised from EtOH to furnish 4-chloro-N-ethylanthranilic acid (2.1 g.), m.p. 214°.

N-ethyl-m-chloroaniline, b.p. 242–244° (Lit.²⁹—243–244°) was formed by decarboxylating the above acid in Ph_2O . It afforded the *tosyl derivative*, m.p. 78° (50% EtOH) (Found : N, 4.57. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClNO}_2\text{S}$ requires : N, 4.52%).

Decarboxylation of (IV) : Formation of (VI). A suspension of (IV) (10 g.) in liquid paraffin (50 ml.) was heated at 290–95° for 1 hr. when CO_2 evolved. Extraction by acid and basification afforded a dark solid (4.2 g.) which was crystallised from 50% EtOH (charcoal) to give (VI) in fine white needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 187°.

By heating (IV) (10 g.) in refluxing Ph_2O (50 ml.) for 1 hr. (VI) (1.3 g.) was obtained similarly.

Cyclisation of diethyl m-chloroanilinomethylenemalonate and isolation of side products (IV), (VI) and (VIII). Diethyl m-chloroanilinomethylenemalonate (297.5 g.) [m.p. 56° (lit²—55–56°). λ_{max} 220, 230 m μ (log ϵ 4.22, 4.47)] was similarly cyclised in Ph_2O (1 L.) and hydrolysed *in situ* to afford the crude acid (I) (210 g.), melting range 262–66° (decomp). Working up of the above crude acid and the Ph_2O layer as before furnished (a) (IV) (2.7 g.), (b) (VIII) (4.5 g.) and (c) (VI) (0.6 g.).

Pyrolysis of Ethyl 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylate (II) : Isolation of (III), (V), (VI) and (VIII) : The ester (II) [m.p. 304° (from AcOH), (lit²—295–297°)] (20 g.) was suspended in Ph_2O (160 ml.) and refluxed for 1 hr. Evolution of CO_2 occurred and a clear solution was formed towards the end. After leaving for 2 days at 25–30° the reaction mixture was filtered and washed with C_6H_6 to afford a creamy white solid (m.p. 285–288°; 13.2 g.) The Ph_2O filtrate and C_6H_6 washings were combined and kept for further working up.

The above solid was hydrolysed with NaOH solution and the pH was adjusted to 9–9.5. The precipitate was collected, washed thoroughly and crystallised from water to

28. P. Cohn, *Monatsh.*, 1901, **22**, 473.

29. I. Heilbron and H. M. Bunbury, *Dictionary of Organic Compounds*, Vol. 2, p. 623, Eyre and Spottiswoode, London (1965).

afford 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline (III) (1.24 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 272°. (lit²—270–272°). The alkaline filtrate, after removal of (III), on acidification, gave the acid (I) [9.8 g.; m.p. 266–268° (decomp)]. Acid extraction of the combined Ph₂O—C₆H₆ solution and basification, furnished 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline, (VIII) (1.8 g.) and 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4(1H)-quinolone (VI) (0.26 g.).

The above Ph₂O—C₆H₆ solution was then washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated *in vacuo* to a small bulk. Addition of petrol ether to the residue gave a dark brownish solid (1.6 g.) which on crystallisation from toluene (charcoal) afforded ethyl 7-chloro-1-ethyl-1 : 4-dihydro-4-oxoquinoline-3-carboxylate (V), m.p. and mixed m.p. 158° (lit¹¹—154–158°).

Pyrolysis of (II) in presence of benzoic acid : A mixture of (II) (10 g.) and benzoic acid (5 g.) was heated at 255° (bath temp.). The mixture gradually liquified and refluxing occurred with evolution of CO₂. After heating for 1 hr. vacuum was applied and a distillate was collected. This was taken up in C₆H₆, washed with Na₂CO₃ solution (10%), and water. On removal of C₆H₆, ethyl benzoate (2.9 g.) [b.p. 213–214°; hydrazide m.p. 112–113° (lit³⁰—111–112.5°)] was obtained.

The residual pyrolysed mixture was treated with benzene and filtered to afford a brown solid (4.8 g.). This was washed with Na₂CO₃ solution (10%) and crystallised from water (charcoal) to afford 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline (III), m.p. and mixed m.p. 272°.

After removal of (III), the benzene solution on evaporation afforded a white solid (0.5 g.), m.p. 275° (EtOH—AcOH) which is insoluble in NaOH (10%) and precipitated unchanged from its solution in conc. HCl on dilution. This was not investigated further.

Pyrolysis of 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII) : 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII) (5 g.) was heated at 250–255° (bath temp.) for 1 hr. On cooling the solid was extracted with hot petrol ether (3 × 50 ml.). The residue on crystallisation from water afforded (VI) (0.65 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 187°.

By working up the petrol ether extract (VIII) (4 g.) was recovered.

Pyrolysis of 7-chloro-4-ethoxyquinoline (VIII) in presence of benzoic acid : A mixture of (VIII) (5 g.) and benzoic acid (3 g.) was heated at 250–255° (bath temp.) for 1 hr. The mixture melted and began to reflux. On cooling C₆H₆ (50 ml.) was added and filtered to yield 7-chloro-4-hydroxyquinoline (3.0 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 272° after crystallisation from water.

Working up of the above benzene solution afforded 7-chloro-1-ethyl-4(1H)-quinolone (0.85 g.) and ethyl benzoate (2.1 g.).